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Double-Active Membranes for a sustainable CO₂ cycle

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EIC Pathfinder Challenge: Carbon dioxide and Nitrogen management and valorisation

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Abstract:This deliverable aims at presenting the first version of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation plan of the DAM4CO₂ project.

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Definitions, Acronyms and Abbreviations

EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
EIC	European Innovation Council
EISMEA	European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
PIC	Participant Identification Code
COO	Coordinator
BEN	Beneficiary

Document History

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Approval History

	Name Surname	Date of Approval
WP Leader	Elisa Esposito	18/04/2024
Coordinator*	Alessio Fuoco	30/04/2024

*on behalf of the EB

Introduction

This deliverable constitutes the deliverable n° D8.2 of the project DAM4CO₂, and it is related to the definition of the Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation Including Communication Activities of the entire project. This document will be used by all the partners as a guideline for the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities. It is a living document that can be modified accordingly to the project needs.

To this regard, **Dissemination** means “make your results public” to whoever can learn from them (scientists, but also policymakers, authorities, industry); **Communication** means “promote your actions and results” to citizen, the media, stakeholders, and **Exploitation** means “make concrete use of results” and this includes commercial purposes as well as societal and political purposes.

The DAM4CO₂ D&E&C plan

The main objective of the dissemination activities is to ensure that the project outcomes and the generated knowledge (concepts, scientific results, methodologies, validated work, problem awareness) are made available to the wider community in a clear, reproducible, and accessible manner. This will involve implementing efficient and effective knowledge management activities, dissemination, exploitation, knowledge transfer and outreach actions.

The dissemination, communication, and exploitation actions of **DAM4CO₂** have been started with the beginning of the project (1st November 2023), will run for the whole duration of the project, and will continue even after the end of the project.

The present plan takes into consideration different stakeholders and the various phases of the project have already been devised with specific objectives:

- to promote the culture of recycling and circular economy among European citizens, and demonstrate how novel membranes can have an impact in this instance;
- to raise awareness of the lower environmental impact and economic feasibility of the **DAM4CO₂** technology, especially for the recovery of valuable components and for separating existing gas streams;
- to build a strong network of stakeholders interested in the project results;
- to guarantee effective knowledge transfer outcomes;
- to enable future exploitation by monitoring the market and business opportunities of CO₂ separation, conversion, and treatment.

The phases

The D&E&C Plan is divided in three phases, backing up the development of the Innovation activities:

Awareness phase (M1 – M12).

At an early stage, it is essential to communicate what the project's scope and objectives are. It is also key to identify the relevant stakeholders for **DAM4CO₂**, as well as to establish contact with similar initiatives. In this phase, the consortium partners will participate in relevant events and conferences, aimed at building new networks and reinforce old ones, and they will contribute to all the communication actions.

Knowledge transfer (M12 – M30).

The second phase aims at providing the first results of the project to the different stakeholders, to raise interest in the exploitation of the next generation membrane materials and processes. The first workshops, webinars and technical papers will start to be delivered.

Replication and exploitation (M30– M36).

The third phase consists in supporting the replication and exploitation actions of **DAM4CO₂**. With the project coming to an end, it will be essential to link the exploitation and dissemination activities to guarantee the future replication of results. The final event will be celebrated openly, and stakeholders will be invited.

Target groups and stakeholders.

A list of stakeholders has already been identified and it is divided into the following seven groups:

- 1) Scientific community: they are interested in research data at lower TRL and the breakthrough of the higher TRL to implement them in similar initiatives.
- 2) Industrial players: considering the innovative scope of the project, it is of particular interest to communicate with the industry to know that the right direction is pursued. They will be one of the main target groups also for exploitation.
- 3) Environmental organization/communities: these include organizations concerned with energy efficiency, circular economy, and waste cycles.
- 4) Professional networks: liaison and cooperation with professional communities and networks are crucial to get wider dissemination to stakeholders.

- 5) Policymakers: this target group must understand the impact of **DAM4CO₂** since they can accelerate public policy implementations in terms of taxes, subsidies, and regulations.
- 6) Media & Press: their involvement guarantees the wider spread of the knowledge and innovation created in **DAM4CO₂**. The press office of the coordinator and other organizations will send press releases for every major event.
- 7) General public: this group includes everyone not included in the previous groups but has some interest in the topic of **DAM4CO₂** or could benefit from this innovation action.

The list will be subjected to continuous update during the lifetime of the project to maximise the outreach of our results and therefore impact.

Tools and channels used to disseminate and communicate.

Many of the tools and channels that are/will be used to disseminate and communicate the obtained results have been already discussed in the “*Deliverable 8.1 - Website and project logo*”. In the previous deliverable, the logo of the project, the website structure and the different social media profiles have been presented. In fact, for a fruitful dissemination and communication, a clear and unique digital identity of the project is essential.

Table 1 reports the dissemination tools of **DAM4CO₂**, the main target groups that will be engaged by them and the expected impact. Indeed, each target group needs specific dissemination and communication channels and strategy.

Table 1. Dissemination & communication tools & channels, addressed target groups and expected impact.

Tools (channel)	Target Groups	Expected impacts
Brochure & Leaflet (Printed materials)	All	Inform about objectives, impacts, methodology, expected and achieved results
Project Website (online)	All	Inform about the project objectives, impacts, expected and achieved results, methodology Keep the stakeholders updated with regular news
Social networks: Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram (Online)	All; Twitter (1,3,5,6,7); LinkedIn (2,4,6); Instagram (6,7 youth!)	Raise awareness on the technology and innovation actions implemented in the project Raise awareness on the economic, societal and scientific impact of the project

Videos and Webinars (Online and Events)	Videos: All Webinars: 1,2,4,5	Communicate the results obtained
Newsletters (online)	All, focus on 2,3,4	
Press release (online, dedicated offices of the institutions)	All, focus on 5,6,7	
Scientific Articles (Publications)	1,2,3,5,6	Communicate the results obtained
Conferences (Events)	1,2,4	<p>Communicate the results</p> <p>Persuade on the benefits to apply the DAM4CO₂ tech & innovation</p> <p>Raise awareness on economic, societal and scientific impact of DAM4CO₂</p>
DAM4CO₂ Workshop (Events)	All	

Brochure & Leaflet

The first version of **DAM4CO₂** Brochure & Leaflet will be created before the first workshop organized by the project (scheduled for June 2024). This will include a short description of the project, partners list/logo, links to the website and social media profiles, and other relevant info. Poster and rollup will also be prepared to be used as communication channel in public events.

Project website

The website of the project is accessible via the link: www.dam4co2.eu. Its structure is described in the previous deliverable. It is the main portal to find all the information related to dissemination and communication activities of the project.

Social Media

DAM4CO₂ has active profile in Instagram, X (ex-twitter), and LinkedIn. They are essential tools for communication with different audience. For instance, while Instagram will be used to engage a “younger” public, the LinkedIn profile will be more focused on professional networking. Due to the always evolving social media/network world a profile on Threads will be activated, if the platform will grow more.

Videos and Webinars

A first video for presenting the overall project has been prepared and added on the project website. The video is also used as first content for the YouTube channel dedicated to the project. It will be also shown in communication events when possible (e.g. booths at fairs, Superscienceme/ European Research nights events). Short videos will be also prepared as insight into the performed research to be shared in the DAM4CO2 YouTube channel.

Webinars will be also organized to communicate and disseminate the project actions and results. They will be recorded and added to the YouTube channel. Part of this activity will be performed within the EIC portfolio actions, since **DAM4CO2** is the leader of the organization of the joint vertical webinars.

NewsLetters

Newsletter will be shared every 6 months with who is interested in the **DAM4CO2** project activities and results. The main distribution channel will be the website and the social media profiles. It will be also distributed by the partners within their contacts and by their official channels.

Press release

Press releases and short news will be prepared and published via the project channels (e.g., social media profiles, website). Major achievement and related press releases will be disseminated and communicated also by the partners channels and dedicated offices. For instance, the press release concerning the starting of the project has been published in English, Italian and Spanish. The press release and associated links are available on our website.

Scientific Articles

DAM4CO2 partners will develop a significant amount of scientific data that will be disseminated by scientific articles in peer-reviewed journals and conferences. Before publication, each article will be subject to internal check to avoid any IP issue, with the procedure agreed by the partners.

Moreover, all the partners will provide Open Access for all the publications produced under the **DAM4CO2** workplan. The type of Open Access will be selected depending on the publication, but always in accordance with the Article 17 of the GA and in line with the FAIR principles and the Data Management Plan of the Project.

Conferences

Participation to conferences and other events is also foreseen by all the consortium partners. Also in this case, before the dissemination of the project results, the partners should agree to the content to avoid any IP issue.

When participating to major events, the partners can also use the Brochure & Leaflet, as well as the poster and rollup to communicate the project actions and results. The presence of project partners to conferences will be announced on the social media of the project and on the NewsLetter in the “upcoming events” section.

DAM4CO₂ Workshop(s)

The consortium will organize a workshop in the final year of the project to disseminate the results and to communicate the benefits of using the technology and science developed within DAM4CO₂. The workshop will be organized in the same venue of a major conference on membranes or on catalysis in Europe to maximize the presence of stakeholders.

Satellite workshops will be also organized by the partners in collaboration with other projects/events. The first satellite workshop is scheduled in June 2024 in Turin.

The impact of dissemination and communication actions will be measured by the Key Performance Indicators defined in the Description of Action of the GA.

Clustering activities by cooperating with similar initiatives

DAM4CO₂ consortium will continue to engage with relevant Horizon Europe projects and other initiatives at European, national and regional/local level in order to maximize cross-pollination of ideas and enhance the benefits of the scientific achievements.

Particular focus will be paid on the cooperation with other projects of the EIC Carbon dioxide and nitrogen management and valorisation portfolio. Networking activities will strength the impact of the project results and activities and dissemination and communication actions can be boosted by joint collaborations, such as the organization of the vertical webinars.

DAM4CO₂ consortium will also network with projects funded by EU calls having complementary scopes such as: HORIZON-CL4-2022-RESILIENCE-01-14 and H2020-LC-SC3-2018-2019-2020, and the national calls based on National Plan of Recovery and Resilience (PNRR) generated by the Next Generation EU action. The objective will be to increase the outreach potential of DAM4CO₂ towards a wider audience and broader stakeholder groups, exploiting the knowledge generated by previous initiatives and establishing synergies, collaborating in many initiatives presented in **Table 1**.

The exploitation strategy

The **DAM4CO₂** consortium will generate IP in several directions throughout the project. However, due to the low Technology Readiness Level of **DAM4CO₂**, at this stage, it is difficult to define the best strategy to fully valorize the results and knowledge created during the execution of the project. For this reason, the exploitation strategy will be updated at any moment, depending on the achieved exploitable results.

The actions on the IPR management will allow the future uptake of the innovation potential in terms of integrated membrane technology spread in the emerging energy market, but even in terms of sharing scientific results. Scientific results will be published only after authorization by all the partners and actors involved in the specific WPs. Innovative intellectual property, as new materials and technology, will be protected through patent filing.

Identified products will be shared into the trade market. Know-how and industrial secrecy are usually part of important and effective protection strategy. Utility models, copyrights and similar strategies will be used for the protection of methodologies and similar results. The protection strategy will depend on the type and readiness level of the results to be exploited, and the consortium will decide by taking the advantages of the expertise of the dedicated offices present in their institutions.

Confidentiality during the execution of the project and before the decision of dissemination and communication, as well as access rights for implementation and exploitation are described in the Consortium Agreement.

Finally, since **DAM4CO₂** is an EIC-pathfinder project, the exploitation of the results will be also oriented toward a technology assessment and upscaling roadmap to identify possible key results to be implemented until reaching the market through the transition and accelerator schemes.

Consortium of DAM4CO₂

Number	Role	Short Name	Legal Name	Country	PIC
1	COO	CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT	999979500
2	BEN	INSTM	CONSORZIO INTERUNIVERSITARIO NAZIONALE PER LA SCIENZA E TECNOLOGIA DEI MATERIALI	IT	999991237
3	BEN	UPV	UNIVERSITAT POLITÈCNICA DE VALÈNCIA	ES	999864846
4	BEN	PRIMALCHIT	PRIMALCHIT SOLUTIONS	ES	892236168
5	BEN	Me-Sep	ME-SEP SPOLKA Z OGRANICZONA ODPOWIEDZIALNOSCIA	PL	887256382
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7	BEN	UEdin	THE UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH	UK	999974941

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**UK Research
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